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Social Media and Early Marriage During the Covid-19 Pandemic in Indonesia

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Abstract

The covid-19 Pandemic has had a tremendous impact on the world community. Indonesia is one of the countries that has felt the impact of the Pandemic. Activities switch to online. Social media is the primary choice for teenagers. Unfortunately, these teenagers consume much harmful content. The novelty in this research is the high number of early marriages in Bantul, Indonesia, during the Pandemic, which is caused by consuming too often social media content that is not educational. This research method is descriptive qualitative. The data collection in this research is Observation, interview, and focus group discussion. The results showed that the number of early marriages during the Pandemic increased 100 percent. One of the causes of the increasing number of early marriages is social media. In addition to social media factors, several other factors cause early marriage during the Pandemic. Lack of positive activities, lots of free time, low education, low knowledge about the purpose of marriage, family economic factors, and promiscuity have led to an increase in the number of early marriages in adolescents during the Pandemic. In addition, early marriage has an impact on the high divorce rate. Researchers conducted socialization about the purpose of marriage from various points of view, both in terms of health, religion, Marriage Law, and family economy. After the researchers conducted FGDs and socialization, the youth of Bantul, Indonesia, understood the real purpose of marriage.

Keywords: Early Marriage, Social Media, Covid-19 Pandemic, Adolescents, Divorce

1. Introduction

Since the Indonesian government officially published that the Corona Virus entered Indonesia in March 2020, Indonesia has become one of the countries exposed to the Pandemic. The number of Covid-19 patients is increasing day by day. In July 2021, new cases were 35,094, an average of 7 days 33,451 (*Number of Covid 19 Patients in Indonesia July 11, 2021 - Google Search*, nd). The government once imposed Large-Scale Social Restrictions at the end of March 2020. The government imposed restrictions on community activities from the beginning of July 2021 until July 20, 2021. The government ordered people to stay at home, work from home, and study online, to suppress the spread of the Coronavirus. In addition, the government is campaigning for the 3M Movement; wear masks, maintain social distance, wash hands. The 3M movement aims to suppress the rate of development of the Corona Virus. When the world changed, interaction shifted to digital platforms, where almost everyone turned to the digital world. Currently, the Internet is no longer just a medium for delivering

electronic mail or looking for news. However, with the Internet, people are starting to recognize social media (Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, and others) and instant messages (WhatsApp, Line, Blackberry Messenger, and others). Internet facilities and content that is increasingly developing mean more and more choices, resulting in increasingly diverse Internet use for each individual. The use of the Internet is reflected in the duration and frequency of accessing the Internet and what facilities are used by internet users when using the Internet (Novianti & Riyanto, 2018).

Research related to the use of social media for adolescents in the UK through interviews with 12 thousand adolescents revealed that 90% of these adolescents were actively using the Internet regularly, and 70% of them had at least one profile on social media (Rianto & Sukmawati, 2021). Until the second quarter, the number of internet users in Indonesia reached 73.7% of the total population of 196.7 million users. They almost penetrated 200 million users from the population of the Republic of Indonesia of 266.9 million (APJII, 2020). The survey results show that teenagers are also the most significant users of the Internet. More than 70% of active internet users come from people aged 13-18 years and are urbanites. These teenagers, often referred to as digital natives, use social media for various purposes, including reading the latest news, entertainment, sharing content they produce themselves, or building relationships with family and close friends (Supratman, 2018).

The novelty in this research is that social media causes early marriage for teenagers in Bantul, Indonesia, during the Covid-19 Pandemic. The number of early marriages or underage in Bantul during the Covid-19 Pandemic rose to 100 percent (Times & Daruwaskita, nd). In connection with the Covid-19 outbreak, many impacts have arisen due to this Corona Virus outbreak. Such as the impact on public health, economy, education, and others. Impact of Education where schools switch to online, causing students to be lazy, play a lot, interact a lot with social media. Social media content that is worrying is information in the form of pornography. Most social media users are teenagers.

At the same time, many internet sites are not suitable for consumption by teenagers (Ulinuha, 2013). Teenagers do direct interaction with the environment is reduced. Teenagers interact a lot through social media, and gadgets are the main item. Many teenagers are exposed to and stimulated by pornographic media content. Teenagers are often exposed to pornographic media content causing pregnancy before marriage which is often called early marriage. Many children who are pregnant under age do not continue their studies, and a divorce occurs, the family economy is not yet established, and is psychologically immature. The description of free sex and underage sex is partly because they do not understand healthy sexual behavior. This is related to the lack of disclosure of information about good and healthy sex in society. There is even a tendency to allow sex to be considered immoral and taboo if discussed openly (Martin, 1992).

Sociology Lecturer at UIN Jakarta, Dr. Ida Rosyidah, MA, explained that early marriage in Indonesia is caused by economic, cultural, state policies, and religious understanding. The poverty rate that increased during the Pandemic caused parents to consider the burden of their lives to be large, thus sacrificing their children to marry at a young age so that the economic burden would be reduced (Rosyida, 2021)

Information media that are spread in society, both through mass and electronic media, become a reference for teenagers about sex. The problem of sexuality cannot be viewed from the side of the transaction of physical relations. Sexuality is a multidimensional phenomenon consisting of biological, psychosocial, behavioral, clinical, moral, and cultural aspects (Masters, Johnson, & Kolodny, 1992).

Departing from the large number of early marriages in Bantul, researchers researched social media and early marriage during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Indonesia. The purpose of this study was to find out the relationship between social media and the prevalence of early marriage among adolescents in Bantul, Indonesia during the Covid-19 Pandemic.

1.1. Social Media

Large social media networks such as Facebook and Twitter have been hailed as drivers of a new, socially engaged educational experience, fostering the capacity for discussion and connection among youngsters (Friesen & Lowe, 2012). Social media facilitates user content depicting opinions, interests, and ideas. Social network websites like Facebook, Twitter, Tumblr, Vine, TikTok, and Instagram are popular among the youth (Anreassen, Pallesen & Griffiths, 2017). The Young educated population is increasingly categorized as the 'digital natives of this information-driven global world (Mohammed et al., 2021). The lifestyle of the world community has been heavily influenced by internet-based technology (Sannusi et al., 2019). Teenagers prefer to spend time accessing the Internet, playing video games, and using smartphones rather than interacting with family, especially mothers and fathers (Hashim & Razali, 2019).

1.2. Adolescent Reproductive Education

The proportion of Indonesia's youth population aged 0-14 years decreased from 44.12 percent in 1971 to 23.33 percent in 2020 (*MaterialBrsInd-20210121151046.Pdf*, nd). The Indonesian population census in 2020 shows that this group constitutes 23.33 percent of the total population of Indonesia. Generation Z was born in 1997 - 2012 with an estimated age of 9 to 24 years. While the millennial generation was born in 1981-1996, the current estimated age is 25-40 years. The married population of Indonesia in 2015 was 72.19 percent. In 2016 it was 68.87 percent, and in 2017 it was 70.78 percent. In the same period, the working-age population aged 15-64 years increased from 53.39 percent to 70.72 percent (*MaterialBrsInd-20210121151046.Pdf*, nd). The percentage of marriages in Indonesia is relatively high, on average, above 50 percent per year of the total population of Indonesia. Together with urbanization and the explosion of information across borders, these significant changes have increased the exposure of young Indonesians to risks associated with reproductive health. The data of the Indonesian health demographic survey in 2017 was found that seven percent of women in the ages 15-19 years is have become mothers, among of them is five percent was labor, and two percent is the first pregnancy (BKKBN, BPS, and Ministry of Health RI, 2018). To protect the negative impact of media exposure to sexy content, sexy attitudes, and others, adolescents should increase positive knowledge about sexual behavior and reproductive Health (Murdiningsih et al., 2020).

Moreover, this result is in line with De Castro et al.'s advice to promote comprehensive sexual and reproductive health education associated with positive perceptions of sexual and reproductive Health in Mexican high school students (de Castro et al., 2018). The importance of sexual education for adolescents. Sexual education is an effort to educate and direct sexual behavior correctly and adequately. Children and adolescents with and without chronic health conditions and disabilities will benefit when they are provided with accurate and developmentally appropriate information about the biological, sociocultural, psychological, relational, and spiritual dimensions of sexuality. Information about sexuality can be taught and shared in schools, communities, homes, and medical offices using evidence-based interventions (Breuner et al., 2016)

The World Health Organization's definition of health is "a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity" (World Health Organization 1946). The definitions of reproductive health and sexual health reflect and extend these definitions of health. Central to our conception of adolescent sexual and reproductive health is understanding adolescence as a life stage defined by the physiological, psychological, social, and cultural transitions that mark the movement from childhood to adulthood. Adolescents emerge as adults, embodying the tension between the need for protection and guidance by parents and adult caregivers, on the one hand, and the rights to autonomy and agency on the other (Schalet et al., 2014).

Teenagers as state assets have become a group that requires special attention. However, specific health problems among adolescents are often overlooked, such as reproductive health, HIV-AIDS, and maternal mortality, the leading causes of morbidity and mortality among adolescents to date (Violita & Hadi, 2019).

The Indonesian Ministry of Health launched an Adolescent-Friendly Health Service program (AFHS) in primary health centers. Within a decade and a half of the program we are running, the number of primary healthcare centers conducting the AFHS has increased and spread fairly in various provinces. The Data Showed that 81.69% of the total districts in Indonesia had at least four primary healthcare centers with AFHS in 2014. This percentage represented about 31% of the total primary healthcare centers in Indonesia (*Pusat Data Dan Informasi - Kementerian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia*, n.d.).

The behavioral approach to sex explains that sexual behavior is a product of biological and psychosocial forces. Thus, behavior is not only studying what humans do but also understanding how and why humans behave. In this case, the term normal or abnormal should not be used, but rather the less or excessive behavior or inappropriate.

The clinical approach emphasizes sex as a natural function. However, physical problems (illness, infection, or medication) can affect sexual response patterns. Likewise, psychological problems (anxiety, sin, shame, depression, or conflict) can interfere with sexuality.

Cultural approaches to sex sometimes cause conflict, but relatively depending on time, place, and circumstances. Morals and rights differ significantly from the cultural background. Likewise, the myth is that women are passive and accepting, while men are more active and aggressive.

Sexual education is an effort to educate and direct sexual behavior correctly and adequately. That is, sexual behavior that emphasizes physical and psychological aspects will lead to or result in healthy sex for both self and others (Widjanarko, 1994). In addition, sexual health problems are also given, which are often associated with various diseases caused by sexual intercourse or commonly known as sexually transmitted diseases (PHS). Various STDs include *gonorrhoea, syphilis, chlamydial infections, chancroid, genital herpes, viral hepatitis, genital warts, molluscum contagiosum, public lice, and vaginal infections* (Master, Johnson & Kolodny, 1992).

The research results conducted by Zelnik and Kim (1982) show that if parents are willing to discuss sex with their children, their children tend to delay premarital sexual behavior. Likewise, Fisher's (1986) research shows that adolescents tend to imitate their parents' behavior. However, it is unfortunate that the information obtained through the mass media is sometimes only fragmentary and generally only emphasizes sex narrowly. However, the problem of sex is not as narrow and straightforward as that.

Bennett and Dickinson's (1980) research states that most teenagers choose to receive early parental sexual education, but adolescents seek information from groups or anywhere because parents do not know or even explain it in detail. Likewise, the research results conducted by Kallen, Stephenson, and Doughty (1983) showed that most adolescents received information about sex through their friends and not through their parents. However, it is different from the results of research by Bennett & Dickinson (1980) and research by Fisher (1986), which states that providing information about sex from parents is not necessarily better than information from other sources.

1.3. Early Marriage

Today, there are an estimated 580 million teenage girls globally, of whom 88 percent live in developing countries (Montazeri et al., 2016). The factors usually put forward as reasons for the early marriage of a girl child are poverty, unwanted pregnancy, parental pressure, peer pressure, and developmental stage. Moreso, it negatively affects the girl child, which includes emotional and mental distress, intolerance, school drop-out, Vesico Vaginal Fistula (VVF) disease, early widowhood, frustration, and hatred for the man as observed by (Kyari, Ayodele, 2014). Meanwhile, early marriage in the view of Islam is to prevent adultery. The Indonesian Ulema Council has issued a *fatwa* about early marriage. According to the MUI, there is no explicit provision regarding the age limit for marriage in the Islamic fiqh literature. Both the minimum and maximum limits.

Allah SWT says, "And marry those who are alone among you and those who are worthy of your male and female slaves." (Surat an-Nur [24]: 32). According to some scholars, what is meant by proper is physical ability. It means having the ability to produce offspring. Age maturity is one indicator for the achievement of marriage goals. The purpose of marriage is the benefit of married life and society and guarantees for pregnancy. Then, the MUI decided for the sake of benefit and referred to the applicable Law (*This is how Islam views early marriage*, 2016). Marriage provisions are returned to the age standardization provisions referring to Law No. 16 of 2019, the text of this article changes to, "Marriage is only permitted if a man and a woman have reached the age of 19 (nineteen) years." (*Law No. 16 of 2019 - Search Google*, nd).

2. Method

This research method is descriptive qualitative. First, in-depth interviews carried out data collection to obtain *here and now constructions* of the people as actors and the problems studied; to events, activities, feelings, motivations, concerns, procedures, habits, structures, patterns, and others. Researchers conducted interviews with 20 sources. The resource persons are teenagers from Sorowajan Village, Bantul, Indonesia. First, interviews to *reconstruct* past social practices. In addition to these two things, interviews are also used to make projections, especially regarding expectations in the future. Second, Observation to see data sources in the form of locations and events. In this study, the Observation was to visit the residences of early married couples in Sorowajan Village, Bantul, Yogyakarta. Third, Focus Group Discussion (FGD), researchers conducted discussions with teenagers, early marriage actors, Sorowajan Hamlet leaders, and Bantul Public Health officers. Fourth, the data analysis technique with three components of analysis: data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing on verification, is carried out in an interactive forum with the data collection process as a cyclical process.

3. Result

The Covid-19 Pandemic has changed the order of human life from all aspects. Public health emergencies can affect individuals' health, safety, and well-being (causing, for example, insecurity, confusion, emotional isolation, and stigma) and communities (due to economic losses, closure of jobs and schools, and inadequate resources for medical care). Poor response and distribution of needs). These effects can translate into various emotional reactions (such as stress or psychiatric conditions), unhealthy behavior (such as excessive substance use), and non-compliance with public health directives (such as home confinement and vaccinations) in people who contract the disease. Disease and in the general population. Extensive research in disaster mental health has established that emotional distress is ubiquitous in affected populations – a finding that is sure to resonate in populations affected by the Covid-19 Pandemic (Pfefferbaum & North, 2020).

One of the impacts of the COVID-19 Pandemic has disrupted students' lives in different ways, not only depending on their level and course of study but also on the point they have reached in their program (Daniel, 2020). Online schools cause many teenage students to play on the Internet. Social media is a favorite medium for teenagers. Using social media becomes a risk to teenagers more often than most adults realize. Most risks fall into the following categories: peer-to-peer, in-appropriate content; lack of understanding of online privacy issues; and outside influences of third-party advertising groups (O'Keeffe et al., 2011). The impact of social media is sexual behavior or the term sexting. Sexting can be defined as "sending, receiving, or forwarding sexually explicit messages, photographs, or images via cell phone, computer, or other digital devices (*Berkshire District Attorney's Office | Mass.Gov*, nd). Many parents today use technology very well and feel comfortable and capable with the online programs and venues for their children and youth. Never-even so, some parents might find it hard to relate to their digital intelligence. Young people are online for several reasons. Such an older adult might not have any basic understanding of establishing these new forms of socialization, which are an integral part of their children's lives (O'Keeffe et al., 2011). This is where the importance of sex education for teenagers. However, the clear goals of the sex education programs depend on the needs of the target population and the context in which sex education is provided (Schaafsma et al., 2017).

3.1. Social Media in Indonesia

Internet penetration in Indonesia at the end of March 2021 was 76.8 percent of the total population. According to Internetworldstats, internet users in the country reached 212.35 million with an estimated total population of 276.3 million. With this achievement, Indonesia is ranked 15th among Asian countries (Kusnandar, 2021). Internet users in Indonesia in early 2021 reached 202.6 million people. This number increased by 15.5 percent or 27 million people when compared to January 2020. The total population of Indonesia itself is currently 274.9 million people. This means that internet penetration in Indonesia in early 2021 will reach 73.7 percent (Media, 2021a). The Statista report noted that the most social media users in Indonesia in 2020 were aged 25-34 years. In detail, male and female users were 20.6% and 14.8%, respectively. The next position is users aged 18-24 years; in detail, male and female users are 16.1% and 14.2%, respectively (Mutia, 2020). These statistics show that internet users among teenagers are high. The following is a table of the most popular social media applications in Indonesia.

Table 1: the most frequently used social media in Indonesia in 2021 (we are social)

(Riyanto, 2021)

- Youtube users in Indonesia are 93.8% of the total population.
- Whatsapp users in Indonesia are 87.7% of the total population.
- Instagram users in Indonesia are 86.6% of the total population.
- Facebook users in Indonesia are 85.5% of the total population.

According to monthly usage, YouTube is the most extensively used social media application in Indonesia, followed by WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter in that order. However, when viewed from the total duration of use of each social media, the Facebook network sits in the top three. They are WhatsApp, where Indonesian social media users spend an average of 30.8 hours per month, then Facebook with 17 hours per month, and Instagram with 17 hours per month (Media, 2021b).

For teenagers in Indonesia, social media is essential. Most teenagers think they are more active in using social media, so people see that they are more modern and easy to get along with. Meanwhile, teenagers who do not have social media are usually considered unmodern and less sociable or outdated. Currently, teenagers in Indonesia are not shy in conveying all their activities into the public space. Social media is a place for socialization, self-actualization, and making friends.

3.2. Social Media and Early Marriage during the Covid-19 Pandemic Early

Marriage is a reality that is often a topic of public discussion, both in actual society and online communities. Early marriage is also a social phenomenon that involves various elements in society, and this is the result of social construction and a new stereotype that has its meaning for the perpetrators. At the same time, early

marriage tends to be positioned on assumptions that have negative connotations because the sacred values of marriage have deviated from the values and norms that grow and develop in society. This is inseparable from the influence of religion, education, modernization, technological advances, and so on media social, thus creating a very free community social interaction with almost no boundaries. Social media is one of the factors that led to early marriage. The consumption pattern of social media is one of the main factors causing early marriage. Therefore, social media plays a significant role in triggering early marriage (Kompasiana.com, 2018).

In addition, the deteriorating economy during the Covid-19 Pandemic has also encouraged early marriage. The United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), in a report, entitled *Adapting to Covid-19: Pivoting The UNFPA-UNICEF Global Program to End Child Marriage to Respond to The Pandemic* predict, four million daughter marriages occur in two years. Next year in the world due to the economic crisis. Then, about 13 million early marriages will occur in the 2020-2030 timeframe in the world. The economic crisis also hit Indonesia during the Covid-19 Pandemic. This country experienced an economic recession in the third quarter of 2020. The number of poor people also increased to 26.4 million, equivalent to 9.8% of the population in March 2020. The Central Statistics Agency (BPS) noted that 3.06% of Indonesian youths who married for the first time under the age of 15 years came from the lowest 40% of household expenditure groups in 2020.

Meanwhile, just 1.85% of the middle 40% expenditure group and 0.91 percent of the top 20% of the economic group are in the top 20%. Young people who married for the first time between 16 and 18 experienced the same thing. The majority (25.79%) came from the bottom 40% of the income distribution. Only 9.27 percent were from the top 20% of the economic category, on the other hand. (Infographic: Child Marriage in Indonesia is Worrying) "This phenomenon cannot be separated from the perspective of families with low economic status who are unable to meet the cost of education and tend to see girls as an economic burden on the family. The solution is to get married as early as possible," the BPS wrote in its report citing the International Center for Research on Women (Jayani, 2021).

According to Bantul youth, in Indonesia, early marriage is commonplace and is considered natural. The number of early marriages or underage in Bantul during the Covid-19 Pandemic rose to 100 percent. Data from the Religious Courts of Bantul Regency, the number of couples who applied for dispensation to marry in 2019 was 125 cases. During 2020 it rose to 246 cases. Meanwhile, until the end of March 2021, there have been 25 cases (Times & Daruwaskita, nd). The number of early marriages continues to grow, so there needs to be a solution. The impact of early marriage is a high divorce rate. Their divorce has also increased. In 2019 or before the Pandemic, 2,018 cases consisted of 1,276 divorced cases and 429 divorced divorces. In 2020 or during the Pandemic, the divorce rate reached 2,052 cases, consisting of 1,159 sued divorces, 425 divorced divorces. Until the end of March 2021, the divorce rate was 445, consisting of 282 divorced lawsuits and 131 divorced divorce (Times & Daruwaskita, nd). Of course, this is very worrying for the future of the youth.

Factors Early marriage occurs because of pregnancy before marriage or cultural, economic, or religious factors. The early marriage caused by pregnancy before marriage usually occurs for several reasons; first, often watching sex videos and pornographic pictures on social media so that teenagers are stimulated to have sex with their partners. Second, the environment of promiscuity that causes pregnancy before marriage. Third, economic factors are caused by low-income families who cannot bear the burden of living with their children, so they are married to more economically capable men. Meanwhile, in early marriages caused by customs or religion, young women do not become pregnant before marriage. The marriage is precisely to avoid free sex and promiscuity.

For teenagers in Bantul, Indonesia, social media is essential. Especially during the Covid-19 Pandemic, many activities are carried out at home. The Indonesian government first implemented Community Activity Restrictions (PPKM) on January 11-25 January 2021. All teaching and learning activities are carried out online (designers, 2021). This causes teenagers to use much time to access the Internet. Unfortunately, teenagers in Bantul, Indonesia, consume harmful internet content that can stimulate sexual behavior before marriage, causing teenage girls to get pregnant.

Researchers conducted interviews and focus group discussions with 20 youths in Bantul, Indonesia. Four were married, and sixteen were unmarried. Some already have children, and some do not. Some already have a lover but are shy in conveying this information. When researchers held discussions on adolescent reproductive health, some of them did not know adolescent reproductive health education information. Some FGD participants did not know the negative impact of having sex at a young age or teenager. Discussions about the risks of early marriage for adolescents who are not ready psychologically, mentally, economically, and with low education cause marriages to become fragile. This is what causes divorce in the household.

The Bantul, Indonesian teenager has a variety of educational backgrounds. Some only graduated from junior high school (SMP), some only graduated from high school (SMA), and the equivalent, some graduated from Strata 1 (S1). Some are already working, and some are not. The amount of free time during the Pandemic makes them spend much time playing on the Internet. They are very active in using social media. The low factor of adolescent education causes them not to have sufficient knowledge of the impact of intimate relationships before marriage. The risk that will be borne when a woman is pregnant before marriage.

In terms of marriage laws, 15 teenagers were unaware of Law 16 of 2019, which amends Law 1 of 1974. They are unaware of the age restriction on marriage imposed by the Law. According to the Law, the minimum marriage age is 19 years both for man and women. What is concerning is the constant presence of mass media, both print and electronic, most notably the Internet, which cannot be controlled within safe limits for public consumption, exposing pornography and scenes that are not deserving of being shown in general, causing an increasing number of modern teenagers to fall into the "permissive society" sphere, which allows them to live any lifestyle they choose (Rifiani, 2011).

4. Discussion

So what is wrong with early marriage? In essence, marriage is human nature. Human nature is to marry, have a family and have children. The primary purpose of marriage is to form a happy family full of peace of love and affection between husband, wife, and children (Prasatiawati, 2017). Marriage aims to create a harmonious family, Sakinah, mawaddah, waRahmah according to religious guidance. Linguistically, sakinah means calm or peaceful, mawaddah means love, and rahmah means love (Islamic Parenting, 2021). Islam teaches its people so that the family is used as an institution that is safe, comfortable, happy, and strong for every family member. The Qur'an and Hadith serve as the foundation for the development of a sakinah family and resolving any issues that may emerge (Prasatiawati, 2017). Thus, there is nothing wrong with teenagers getting married if they have the right goals and guidance. If the teenager is ready to marry, meaning that he is ready both mentally, economically, psychologically, physically, and from the side of the Islamic religion to avoid adultery, then the marriage will be good, it is recommended. However, if the opposite happens, then marriage becomes a problem. Teenagers have sex before marriage, adultery occurs, and pregnancy occurs, while they are not emotionally, economically, and mentally ready. Things like this are prohibited both from the side of Islam, the Law, community norms, and customs.

According to the research results of the mother and child (Ali, 2018), the impact of early marriage affect various aspects of life, especially the quality of maternal and infant quality as follows below:

1. Quality of others

- Early Pregnancymake mothers lack nutrients for themselves
- and increased risk of anemia the incidence of depression
- Risk of dying at an early age
- Increased maternal mortality
- According to the epidemiological study of young mothers with cervical cancer. The younger a woman has her first child, the more susceptible she is to cervical cancer.
- The risk of getting sexually transmitted diseases.

2. Quality of Children

- Birth weight tends to be lower because the nutritional needs of pregnant women must be higher, and both of them are in dire need of nutrition.

- Babies are born malnourished, therefore, susceptible to diseases that result in death.
3. Household Quality
- Many early marriages are directly proportional to the divorce rate so that many divorce cases are the impact of early marriage.
 - Incompatibility between parents and in-laws.
 - Inability to adapt and socialize.
 - Economic limitations because they do not have decent jobs and create a poor generation.
4. Domestic Violence, Death, and Dropouts.
- According to the results of the Humanitarian Organization's research on child protection, as many as 44% of girls who marry at an early age experience Domestic Violence (KDRT) with high-frequency levels. On the other hand, 56% of girls experience low-frequency domestic violence. In addition to the high rate of Domestic Violence (KDRT), early marriage also impacts the reproductive health of girls. Girls aged 10-14 years are five times more likely to die during pregnancy or childbirth than girls aged 20 to 25 years. If the child is 15-19 years old, it is twice as likely.
5. Disconnected Education Level
- Early marriage indeed results in the child not being able to achieve higher education. From the Humanitarian Organization research results, only 5.6% of children who marry at an early age continue their education after marriage, and the rest drop out of school because they carry out domestic life. However, their household very rarely achieves a prosperous family.
6. Population surge
- Early marriage is one of the contributors to the population jump; it can be seen that currently, the population of West Java has reached 43 million people with a growth rate of almost 2% per year.

The youth of Bantul, Indonesia, finally realized that early marriage was not prohibited, as long as it followed the existing signs. The signs are from the side of Islamic religious Law. From the side of the Marriage Law, it meets the requirements so that it is legal, does not violate community norms, and does not violate customs. Thus, adolescents are ready from an economic, mental, physical, and spiritual perspective.

The researcher and the team conducted Focus Group Discussions (FGD) and socialization of early marriage and sex education to teenagers in Bantul, Indonesia. The FGD invited resource persons from teenagers, early marriage actors, Sorowajan Hamlet leaders, and Bantul Community Health officers in Sorowajan village, Indonesia. The researcher's initial discussion asked about the concept of marriage according to Bantul teenagers. It turns out that almost all do not understand the importance of marriage and the purpose of marriage. Researchers asked about online schools for teenagers. They answer that the implementation of online schools causes them to be free to consume content that is not educational. Free time is used for dating, so pregnancy occurs before marriage. This marriage is still very premature because they are not ready for mental, psychological, physical, economic, and knowledge. The result is a divorce.

After we discussed, the result is that the teenagers finally realized that early marriage, because they were pregnant before marriage or because of free sex, would bear a heavy risk. After the researchers conducted socialization, they could describe the impact of early marriage due to pregnancy before marriage or free sex: major sins for having committed adultery, family responsibilities, unfinished school, not working, and being excommunicated from the environment.

They realize that early marriage is precarious, especially in terms of women's health, especially pregnant at a young age which is very risky for the birth process and the health of the uterus. Additionally, young couples are more vulnerable to their social surroundings and have not been able to take responsibility for all of their responsibilities; as a result, they occasionally face a mental shock due to their still unstable mental attitude and emotional state. ripe. While social media can be more beneficial for educational purposes than for browsing irrelevant items.

In summary, early marriage is nothing new. Early marriage has been around for a long time, but the problem is that early marriage has increased by 100 percent during the Covid-19 Pandemic in Bantul, Indonesia. The

research findings are that many teenagers in Bantul, Indonesia, do not know the importance of marriage and the purpose of marriage. The influence of social media is powerful, especially content that is not educational, pornographic, and porno action. During the Pandemic, schools enforce online learning, causing students to be free to consume content that is not educational. Free time is used for dating, so pregnancy occurs before marriage. This marriage is still very premature because they are not ready for mental, psychological, physical, economic, and knowledge. The impact of the marriage is divorce. After the researchers and the team conducted FGDs, discussed, and provided socialization of the importance of marriage and its purpose for teenagers, they understood. Bantul youth have opened their horizons about the nature of marriage and the purpose of marriage. Social media can be used for more positive things than viewing content that is not educational.

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References

- Andreassen, CS, Pallesen, S., & Griffiths, MD (2017). The relationship between addictive use of social media, narcissism, and self-esteem: Findings from a large national survey. *Addictive Behaviors*, 64, 287-293.
- Ali, S. (2018). The Teen Marriage in Indonesia on the Country Perspective and Religion as Well as the Problem. *Jurnal Legislasi Indonesia*, 12(2), Article 2. <https://e-jurnal.peraturan.go.id/index.php/jli/article/view/405>
- This is How Islam Views Early Marriage*. (2016). *Republika Online*. <https://republika.co.id/berita/dunia-islam/fatwa/16/07/14/oaampg313-begini-islam-memandang-pernikahan-dini>
- Berkshire District Attorney's Office | Mass.gov*. (nd). Retrieved August 10, 2021, from <https://www.mass.gov/orgs/berkshire-district-attorneys-office>
- Breuner, CC, Mattson, G., Adolescence, CO, & Health, C. on PA of C. and F. (2016). Sexuality Education for Children and Adolescents. *Pediatrics*, 138(2). <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2016-1348>
- BKKBN, BPS, and Kemenkes RI, "Indonesian Health Demographic Survey," Usaid, pp. 1-606, 2018.
- Daniel, SJ (2020). Education and the COVID-19 Pandemic. *PROSPECTS*, 49(1), 91-96. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-020-09464-3>
- de Castro, F., Rojas-Martínez, R., Villalobos-Hernández, A., Allen-Leigh, B., Breverman-Bronstein, A., Billings, DL, & Uribe-Zúñiga, P. (2018). Sexual and reproductive health outcomes are positively associated with comprehensive sexual education exposure in Mexican high-school students. *PloS One*, 13(3), e0193780. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0193780>
- detiknews. (2021). *The meaning of PPKM, its abbreviation and its rules*. <https://news.detik.com/berita/d-5640047/makna-ppkm-kepanjangan-hingga-aturannya>
- Friesen, N., & Lowe, S. (2012). The questionable promise of social media for education: Connective learning and the commercial imperative. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 28(3), 183-194. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2729.2011.00426.x>
- Hashim, N., & Razali, A. (2019). Technology and Social Media in Communication between Mothers, Fathers, and Children. *Jurnal Komunikasi: Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 35(4), Article 4. <http://ejournal.ukm.my/mjc/article/view/36836>

- Jayani, D. H. (2021). *The Epidemic of Early Marriage in the Midst of the Pandemic and its Bad Impact — Analisis Data Katadata*. <https://katadata.co.id/muhammadridhoi/analisisdata/5ff7cb5cdf279/wabah-pernikahan-dini-di-tengah-pandemi-dan-dampak-buruknya>
- Jumlah pasien covid 19 indonesia tgl 11 juli 2021 [Amount of Covid-19 patients 11 July 2021] (nd). Retrieved July 11, 2021, from <https://www.google.com/search?q=jumlah+pasien+covid+19+indonesia+tgl+11+juli+2021&client=firefox-bd&sxsr>
- Kompasiana.com. (2018, December 16). *Media and Early Marriage*. KOMPASIANA. <https://www.kompasiana.com/andrynugraha/5c1662ec677ffb720121f262/media-dan-pernikahan-dini>
- Kusnandar, VB (2021). *Indonesia's internet penetration ranks 15th in Asia in 2021* | Databoks. <https://databoks.katadata.co.id/datapublish/2021/07/12/penetrasi-internet-indonesia-urutan-ke-15-di-asia-pada-2021>
- Kyari, Ayodele, GV, Joseph. (2014). *The Socio-Economic Effect of Early Marriage in North Western Nigeria | Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*. 5 No 14. <https://www.richtmann.org/journal/index.php/mjss/article/view/3190>
- MateriBrsInd-20210121151046.pdf*. (nd). Retrieved August 9, 2021, from https://www.bps.go.id/website/materi_ind/materiBrsInd-20210121151046.pdf
- Media, KC (2021a, February 23). *Number of Indonesian Internet Users in 2021 Reaches 202 Million*. KOMPAS.com. <https://tekno.kompas.com/read/2021/02/23/16100057/jumlah-pengguna-internet-indonesia-2021-tembus-202-juta>
- Media, KC (2021b, February 24). *Research Reveals More Than Half of Indonesia's Population is "Literate" on Social Media*. KOMPAS.com. <https://tekno.kompas.com/read/2021/02/24/08050027/riset-ungkap-lebih-dari-separuh-penduduk-indonesia-melek-media-sosial>
- Mohammed, MTS, Ibrahim, F., & Yunus, N. (2021). Exploring The Relationship of Social Media Usage and Multitasking of Social Media on Self-Efficacy and Academic Performance. *Jurnal Komunikasi: Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 37(1), Article 1. <http://ejournal.ukm.my/mjc/article/view/45631>
- Montazeri, S., Gharacheh, M., Mohammadi, N., Alaghand Rad, J., & Eftekhari Ardabili, H. (2016). Determinants of Early Marriage from Married Girls' Perspectives in Iranian Setting: A Qualitative Study. *Journal of Environmental and Public Health*, 2016, e8615929. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/8615929>
- Murdiningsih, M., Rohaya, R., Hindun, S., & Ocktariyana, O. (2020). The effect of adolescent reproductive health education on premarital sexual behavior. *International Journal of Public Health Science (IJPHS)*, 9(4), 327. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijphs.v9i4.20444>
- Mutia, CA (2020). *What is the Age of the Majority of Social Media Users in Indonesia?* | Databoks. <https://databoks.katadata.co.id/datapublish/2020/11/23/berapa-usia-mayoritas-pengguna-media-sosial-di-indonesia>
- Novianti, R., & Riyanto, S. (2018). Media Literacy Level of Village Adolescents in Using the Internet. *Jurnal Komunikasi Pembangunan*, 16(2), 158–171. <https://doi.org/10.46937/16201825628>
- O'Keeffe, GS, Clarke-Pearson, K., & Council on Communications and Media. (2011). The Impact of Social Media on Children, Adolescents, and Families. *PEDIATRICS*, 127(4), 800–804. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2011-0054>
- Parenting Islami. (2021). *It turns out this is the meaning of Sakinah Mawaddah Warahmah which is often said to newlyweds, Masya Allah!* <https://www.orami.co.id/magazine/sakinah-mawaddah-warahmah/>
- Pfefferbaum, B., & North, CS (2020). Mental Health and the Covid-19 Pandemic. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 383(6), 510–512. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMp2008017>
- Prasetyawati, E. (2017). *View of Penafsiran Ayat-Ayat Keluarga Sakinah, Mawaddah, Wa Rahmah dalam Tafsir Al-Misbah dan Ibnu Katsir*. <https://e-journal.metrouniv.ac.id/index.php/nizham/article/view/993/836>
- Pusat Data dan Informasi—Kementerian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia*. (nd). Retrieved August 9, 2021, from <https://pusdatin.kemkes.go.id/folder/view/01/structure-publikasi-pusdatin-info-datin.html>
- Rianto, P., & Sukmawati, AI (2021). Literasi Digital Pelajar di Yogyakarta: Dari Consuming ke Prosuming Literacy. *Jurnal Komunikasi Global*, 10(1), 137–159. <https://doi.org/10.24815/jkg.v10i1.20612>
- Rifiani, D. (2011). Early Marriage in the Perspective of Islamic Law. *Journal de Jure*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.18860/j-fsh.v3i2.2144>
- Riyanto, AD (2021). *Hootsuite (We are Social): Indonesian Digital Report 2021 – Andi Dwi Riyanto, Dosen, Praktisi, Konsultan, Pembicara: E-bisnis/Digital Marketing/Promotion/Internet marketing, SEO, Technopreneur, Fasilitator Google Gapura Digital yogyakarta*. <https://andi.link/hootsuite-we-are-social-indonesian-digital-report-2021/>
- Rosyida, I. (2021). Highlight the High Rate of Early Marriage during the Pandemic. *RDK FM UIN JAKARTA*. <http://rdk.fidkom.uinjkt.ac.id/index.php/2021/06/19/soroti-tingginya-angka-pernikahan-dini-di-masa-pandemi/>

- Sannusi, SN, Ibrahim, F., Shaari, AH, & Subhi, N. (2019). Use of Social Media among B40 Youth around the Klang Valley. *Jurnal Komunikasi: Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 35(4), Article 4. <http://ejournal.ukm.my/mjc/article/view/31578>
- Schaafsma, D., Kok, G., Stoffelen, JMT, & Curfs, LMG (2017). People with Intellectual Disabilities Talk About Sexuality: Implications for the Development of Sex Education. *Sexuality and Disability*, 35(1), 21–38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11195-016-9466-4>
- Schalet, AT, Santelli, JS, Russell, ST, Halpern, CT, Miller, SA, Pickering, SS, Goldberg, SK, & Hoenig, JM (2014). Invited Commentary: Broadening the Evidence for Adolescent Sexual and Reproductive Health and Education in the United States. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 43(10), 1595–1610. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-014-0178-8>
- Supratman, LP (2018). Penggunaan Media Sosial oleh Digital Native. *Jurnal ILMU KOMUNIKASI*, 15(1), 47–60. <https://doi.org/10.24002/jik.v15i1.1243>
- Times, IDN, & Daruwaskita. (nd). *Pandemic, Early Marriage Rates in Bantul Soar by 100 Percent*. IDN Times. Retrieved August 14, 2021, from <https://jogja.idntimes.com/news/jogja/daruwaskita/pandemik-angka-pernikahan-dini-di-bantul-melonjak-hingga-100-persen>
- Ulinnuha, M. (2013). Protecting Children From Negative Internet Content: A Study of Children's Specific Web Browsers. *Sawwa: Jurnal Studi Gender*, 8(2), 341–360. <https://doi.org/10.21580/sa.v8i2.661>
- Undang-undang pernikahan terbaru 2020—Penelusuran Google* [2020 latest marriage law] (n.d.). Retrieved August 27, 2021, from <https://www.google.com/search?client=firefox-b-d&q=undang-undang+pernikahan+terbaru+2020> BKKBN, BPS, and Kemenkes RI, “Survei Demografi Kesehatan Indonesia,” Usaid, pp. 1-606, 2018.